

water was also taken through the whole process. The results are recorded in the Table.

TABLE: ESTIMATION OF THIOCYANATE, THIOUREA AND PHENYLTHIOUREA

Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	Error (mg)
	Thiocyanate	
2.18	2.18	0.00
2.72	2.72	0.00
3.26	3.25	-0.01
3.81	3.80	-0.01
4.35	4.35	0.00
4.89	4.88	-0.01
5.44	5.43	-0.01
	Thiourea	
2.85	2.85	0.00
3.56	3.55	-0.01
4.28	4.28	0.00
4.99	5.00	+0.01
5.70	5.72	+0.02
7.13	7.09	-0.04
	Phenylthiourea	
5.60	5.70	+0.10
7.00	6.97	-0.03
8.20	8.23	+0.03
9.40	9.0	+0.10
10.60	10.77	+0.17
11.40	11.40	0.00
12.80	12.86	+0.06

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Synthesis of 1-(*p*-Carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-Trimethyl-2-Pyrazoline. Its Amides, Esters, Hydrazide, Benzylidenes and Thiosemicarbazid Derivatives

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PYRAZOLINES were first reported by Knorr and Blank¹. 1-Phenyl pyrazoline was obtained by Fischer and Knoevenagel² from phenylhydrazine and acrolein, instead of the expected hydrazone. It was

found by v. Auwers and Voss³ that pyrazolines are formed when α, β unsaturated carbonyl compounds reacted with arylhydrazines. They also found that when the hydrazones were isolable, treatment with acetic acid caused rearrangement to the corresponding pyrazoline.

p-Carboxyphenylhydrazine has been used as a carbonyl reagent by Veibel⁴. He also found that α, β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds reacted with *p*-carboxyphenyl hydrazine to form 1-aryl-2-pyrazolines.

p-Carboxyphenylhydrazine reacted with mesityl oxide to give 1-(*p*-carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline (I).

IR ν_{max} Nujol: 1600, 1660, 2900-2960 cm^{-1} .

N.M.R. ($\text{CCl}_4 + \text{D}_2\text{O}$): δ 11.5, 7.98 $J = 8$ cps; δ 7.22, $J = 8$ cps; δ 2.82, 2.05 and 1.55.

The above values are in keeping with the structure assigned.

Experimental

1-(*p*-Carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline (I):

To *p*-carboxyphenylhydrazine hydrochloride (0.1 mole), dissolved in 50% ethanol (150 ml) was added freshly distilled mesityl oxide (0.1 mole), and the